

**Does Instrumental Spanish Music Enhance the Comprehension of Spanish Reading Among
Private School Students in Spanish Classes?**

Word Count:

Introduction

Research across cognitive psychology and foreign language learning indicates that background music interacts with the key components of cognitive processing systems used in reading, attention, memory, and comprehension (Anderson & Fuller, 2010). Studies consistently show that music alters cognitive function in reading. Still, these effects vary in several aspects of the background music, including lyrics, tempo, beats per minute (BPM), and the linguistic demands of the text. Background music with lyrics impairs comprehension of text, as the brain struggles to process the words from the music alongside those of the text. This challenges the brain as it overloads the cognitive system used for language comprehension (Anderson & Fuller, 2010). This supports the notion that music contains linguistic information and engages processing mechanisms similar to those used for understanding written language (Renkewitz, 2011). Second-language interference increases when learners are reading and learning a new language. Background music influences reading time, fixation patterns, and comprehension accuracy, demonstrating a cognitive change when learning a new language (Sun et al. 2024). A substantial amount of research focuses on vocabulary learning, suggesting attention and performance in foreign language acquisitions can be improved with instrumental music that has a moderate tempo (Baďurova, 2019). This is supported through neuroscientific studies that show instrumental music helps reduce mental fatigue and improves verbal memory as it reduces prefrontal cortex activity associated (Ferreri et al., 2013). Electroencephalogram, or EEG, research suggests that instrumental music changes the way neural activity works, increasing cognitive strain during reading comprehensions. The literature review identified cultural and linguistic factors that are significant as they influence learners' engagement and comprehension. Research shows that

students who have cultural background knowledge of the foreign text perform better in reading comprehension tasks (Erten, Ismail hakkı & Razi, 2009). This is shown in other studies, as research has concluded that students had improved focus and reduced anxiety when listening to music that had a linguistic alignment to the text they were reading, reporting feeling more confident and encouraged (Kim, Hyun-Ju, et al, 2024). Emotional and cognitive improvements are supported by its connection to the Mozart effect, a short-term enhancement that has been shown to improve focus in listeners. Suggesting that a pleasant, moderate tempo of instrumental music is the appropriate condition for a comprehension task in a research experiment, being shown to be a cognitive performance enhance (Thompson et al., 2001). From a neuroscientific standpoint, music and language share overlapping neural pathways, with predictable rhythmic structures potentially facilitating linguistic processing (Moreno & Besson, 2006). Yet a gap is shown, no study has examined whether instrumental music that is linguistically aligned with the target reading text, specifically, instrumental Spanish music and Spanish text, improving comprehension in L2 learners. My experiment aims to test whether instrumental Spanish music supports comprehension of Spanish reading passages by aligning linguistic familiarity with instrumental Spanish music and Spanish text, testing comprehension levels. Addressing this gap is significant as it gives language educators, L2 learners, immigrants, and more to have better comprehension of foreign text. By comparing a silence, instrumental Spanish music, and instrumental English music groups, this study is able to isolate the effects of linguistic alignment while controlling for the general effect of music. With implications for L2 learners to improve foreign language reading comprehension.

Literature Review

The use of background music is used in many experiments in cognitive psychology, neuroscience, and second language learning (Anderson & Fuller, 2010). These experiments tend to focus on and measure the effects of background music on attention, comprehension, and memory in the tasks given by researchers. Researchers in these studies have commonly concluded that background music changes the cognitive processing system that's used for reading, claiming that the tempo, arousal level, lyrics, beats per minute(BPM), and cultural familiarity play a role in how it changes one's processes and outcome of the background music (Thompson et al., 2001). Synthesis shows that the right type of background music, like instrumental music, can support reading comprehension by leveraging the cognitive load, increasing focus, and improving mood (Ferreri et al., 2013). This literature review synthesizes evidence from five key thematic areas to situate the current study within its research field to help understand the gap of my research experiment and answer my research question, Does Instrumental Spanish Music Enhance the Comprehension of Spanish Reading Among Private School Students in Spanish Classes?

Lyrical music and cognitive interference

When playing lyrical background music during an academic task, the verbal words from the music tend to interfere and overload the cognitive processing system when performing the task (Renkewitz, 2011). A common theme across the researchers is that lyrical music harms reading comprehension as it interferes with verbal comprehension. A study with middle school students, tasked with a reading task, was suppressed by lyrical music conditions. This is because lyrics take up space in the cognitive system, making it harder for the students to focus and comprehend the reading task (Anderson & Fuller, 2010). Meta-analysis shows that instrumental music has a more supportive feature as it is background music without any lyrics, meaning there

isn't any linguistic interference (Renkewitz, 2011). EEG readings show that background music loads the semantic processing system with lyrics and linguistic tasks with a greater amplitude to come from the cognitive system (Du, 2020). These amplitudes have harmonic comprehension levels as they interfere with the semantic system when there is a harmonic change (Calma-Roddin & Drury, 2020). With all this, removing background music with lyrics is the best way to conduct my experiment for greater stability in the results of my findings in supporting, not harming, reading comprehension.

Background music in L2 learning

Background music in L2 learning. L2 learning, or second language learning, in research proves that the use of background music in L2 learning influences reading time, memory, and comprehension when compared to learning their native language (Sun et al., 2024). EFL or English foreign language, Chinese learners who have been researched on have shown a negative effect from lyrical music when learning English, and a positive effect or minimal effect with instrumental music (Su et al., 2023). Classical and instrumental music and lyrical music have reported different outcomes in research that was conducted on L2 participants learning Indonesian vocabulary, stating that instrumental music helps comprehension while pop music helps recall (Groot, 2006). Tempo is another key factor when conducting these experiments. Similarly, steady tempo instrumental music has been shown to help L2 participants complete Mandarin tasks in short and long-term recall. Researchers concluded that the rhythmic aspect of the background music plays an important role in the attention and retention of recall (Williamson & Kang, 2012).

Cultural and linguistic familiarity. Cultural familiarity is a repeating factor in this field of research; studies show that students have an easier time understanding a reading task when they

can recognize the cultural background of the text, which increases their comprehension (Erten & Razi, 2009). English learning Spanish students performed better in an experiment when they were given tasks when the English reading passages had culturally familiar content (Erten & Razi, 2009). Researchers found that anxiety levels decreased and motivations increased when L2 learners listened to background music that was associated with the same language that they were learning (Kim et al., 2024). Unfamiliar background music harms comprehension by increasing the cognitive load, while familiar background music supports it, as supported by studies with EEG scans that show familiarity in the type of background music helps participants have a reduced cortical interference (Brown & Kang, 2022). These findings helped me form my hypothesis, as research in the field has shown that cultural background and linguistic familiarity do help L2 participants' attention retention and comprehension while reducing anxiety, meaning that instrumental Spanish music helps students' comprehension of Spanish reading texts.

Neural overlap between music and language. The brain's neural system has an overlap when you have lyrical music and reading words, going into the same cognitive load. Several studies on neuroscience have shared a common idea that music and language use the same neural pathways to interpret and manage linguistic words. A study that was conducted on musically trained children concluded that because of their training, the children grew a stronger neural sensitivity, which correlated to improved grammar, demonstrating the overlap between the neural pathways used for music and language learning. (Moreno & Besson, 2006). Studies have supported this with the claim that predictable instrumental music helps the process of linguistic development, and harmonic changes in the background music harmed participants by causing interference (Peretz et al., 2015). This suggested that something like predictable instrumental

Spanish music with a steady rhythm helps participants comprehend Spanish text by using the same neural system.

Classroom research and individual differences. Research that's been done in a classroom environment promotes instrumental music as a buffer to students' concentration while reducing anxiety and arousal. This has been demonstrated with classical instrumental music improving reading and writing among elementary school students, as their performance in reading tasks with a stabilized mood and more focused attention (Hallam et al., 2002). On the other hand, research has shown that introverted students perform better in silence, while extroverted students perform better with music, showing a personal difference in the way the music affects their learning (Miranda & Claes, 2009). This goes along with other research that claims that students who typically study with music can perform better in these experiments with background music, while students who don't typically use music in their studying and learning are more likely to perform worse with the background music in the experiment (Goltz & Sadakata, 2021). With this, differences among individual students are acknowledged as moderating variables, considering their background, study habits, and personality traits; with possible effects on the experiment's background conditions effect.

In this field of research, many experiments are conducted to investigate various topics. A common finding in this field of research is that lyrics hinder comprehension due to overload, which causes semantic interference. Different research has concluded different effects that come from instrumental music, mainly claiming that the music effect is supportive or neutral. Instrumental music that has a moderate tempo is reported to increase attention and mood in experiments with researchers, suggesting that the shared neural pathways connect the rhythmic aspect of the music to comprehension of a new language. Researchers have shown that having a

cultural familiarity with a reading task improves motivation levels, along with comprehension. A gap remains, as no research has examined whether background music, aligned with the language of the text, improves the comprehension of L2 learners trying to learn a new language. I hypothesize that if Spanish students are reading Spanish text, their comprehension, attention, and accuracy will increase with instrumental Spanish music. Playing instrumental Spanish music during Spanish reading will fill the gap of whether or not linguistic familiarity in instrumental music supports L2 in reading comprehension. My experiment will fill this gap in the field to help anyone trying to learn a new language by synthesizing and comparing silence, instrumental English music, and instrumental Spanish music.

My study used an experimental design to test the hypothesis of instrumental Spanish music improving the comprehension of private school Spanish students. The experimental method was the best choice as it allowed me to compare groups of instrumental Spanish, silence, and instrumental English, helping me to control confounding variables that could change the attention and/or comprehension in the results. An experimental design is commonly used in my field of research, background music influencing participants' cognitive processing, changing reading time, accuracy, and memory, in a measurable way (Anderson & Fuller, 2010; Sun et al., 2024). The experimental method allows me to isolate the effects of the language of the music while looking at the correlation between the music and the language being learned, testing whether instrumental music in the same language as the text improves L2 learners' comprehension (Renkewitz, 2011; Du, 2020). Based on the evidence reviewed, it was hypothesized that Spanish III students read Spanish text while listening to instrumental Spanish music, followed by silence, with the instrumental English Music condition producing the lowest scores due to cross linguistic interference.

Methodology

Participants were students in Spanish III classes at a private high school. Spanish III is an appropriate level of Spanish as it's an intermediate level in high school, where the students have a good understanding when compared to students in Spanish I, but are not experts like the students at an AP level. Research shows that an intermediate level is appropriate for research, as students at a moderate level will show a bigger change from the effects of the background music when completing comprehension tasks (Groot, 2006; Williamson & Kang, 2012). Students in Spanish III have another advantage over Students in Spanish I, as they've had more years of experience with more cultural familiarity. This affects comprehension in L2 learners, as they are likely to do better if they have already been exposed to the environment and tasks in my experiment. This will help me collect consistent results (Erten & Razi, 2009).

My Spanish teacher provided me with the Spanish III textbook that's used in the classes circular, "Reporteros 3: student textbook", meaning they're an appropriate fit for the Spanish III students. I used five different passages, one passage per day, and each group will be given the same passage each day. Having a controlled and similar-length text is important for the experiment, as using text that varies could change comprehension scores (Hallam et al., 2002). These passages were meant to take the students ten minutes to read and complete the comprehension questions. Using an appropriate reading level is important, as using difficult passages can harm the experiment's findings by negatively reducing the effects that come from background music (Sun et al., 2024). The experiment used three background conditions: silence, instrumental Spanish music, and instrumental English music. In the silence condition, students are to complete the task in silence without any background noise, acting as a baseline for the experiment, as research shows that students have their best performance when they have no

auditory distractions, increasing their accuracy and comprehension in silence (Hallam et al., 2002). Instrumental English music allowed me to compare the effects of the music being culturally unfamiliar, testing whether the language of the music influences Spanish reading comprehension, isolating the language and not just the type of music (Groot, 2006). By having a musical condition of instrumental English music and instrumental Spanish music, I can determine whether having the text and music in the same language improves comprehension with cultural and linguistic similarities. Research has shown that listening to music in the language you are learning can improve L2 learners' focus while reducing anxiety (Kim et al., 2024; Brown & Kang, 2022). The instrumental tracks were chosen instead of lyrical music, as lyrics interfere with the cognitive processing system used for reading comprehension (Anderson & Fuller, 2010; Renkewitz, 2011). The experiment used a tempo of 80-100 BPM, beats per minute, for the instrumental music, as this tempo is a moderate range that has been shown to improve and affect mood without arousing students (Thompson et al., 2001). This allowed me to better test my hypothesis, as the music wouldn't be distracting the students because of the moderate tempo. (Bottiroli et al., 2014).

At the end of the week, I gave students a ten-question Likert scale survey that asked them to reflect on their focus, calmness, motivation, and confidence throughout the week while completing the reading task with their set background condition. The purpose of the survey is to measure how the students' reading comprehension was affected by background music, giving me qualitative data to synthesize the results of the experiment. The responses from the surveys are an effective means of collecting data with L2 learners, as other variables like anxiety and motivation can change the effects that background music has (Kim et al., 2024). By asking students if they typically study and learn with or without music, I can determine whether their

study habits may have changed their performance while completing the reading comprehension tasks and listening to music (Goltz & Sadakata, 2021).

The study was conducted over five school days, Monday through Friday, during which students listened to their assigned group music condition while completing a ten-minute Spanish reading comprehension task. Students began the task at the start of class and were given ten minutes to finish. A short and timed task at the start of class is optimal for the experiment, as it limits fatigue, which shows the different effects of the background music (Su et al., 2023). I randomly assigned class periods to music conditions to avoid bias, as certain characteristics from class periods could have been looked at and chosen in specific ways to support my findings. This keeps the study and students more honest about their focus levels in the experiment (Kim et al., 2024).

Data will be collected from the reading comprehension multiple choice questions, the comprehension scores will be collected after each day, and will be averaged for each music condition. The mean accuracy scores are used in this field of experimental research on reading and music cognition research to compare the effectiveness of treatment among experimental groups (Hallam et al., 2002). By having a standard deviation, I can calculate the inconsistent performance that the music may have caused within each music condition; distraction, confounding variables, and conditions can increase variability. (Du, 2020). Comprehension scores from the three music conditions will be compared to determine which condition had the highest mean score; the group with the highest average score is the group associated with the best comprehension. Research compares and synthesizes the groups to measure the effectiveness of different background conditions on reading comprehension (Anderson & Fuller, 2010). The responses from the surveys are analyzed and synthesized to see if students felt focused, anxious,

and motivated. The mixed-methods approach to the survey is common in research on how background music affects cognitive processes. (Thompson et al., 2001; Kim et al., 2024).

Ethics approvals were obtained from the school, rather than through the traditional formal IRB review process. Approval for conducting the experiment in written form was acquired from the administration of the educational facility before the commencement of the experiment. Consent was sought from the teacher in charge of the classroom lessons. The identity of the children involved was not collected, and all scores were anonymous. None of the students changed their conduct in any way beyond what was normal for reading tasks as required by the lessons at the time, and no deception was involved.

Results

Table 1 presents the mean comprehension scores and standard deviation for each background music condition across the five trials. Figure 1 displays the overall mean score by condition alongside trials by trial performance trends.

Table 1

Mean comprehension score(%), by background music condition across five trials

Condition	Trial 1	Trial 2	Trial 3	Trial 4	Trial 5	Overall M (SD)
Silence (Period 2)	72.94	72.94	75.29	71.76	70.59	72.71 (20.67)
Spanish Music (Period 4)	80.00	71.76	75.29	72.94	75.29	75.06 (22.45)
English Music (Period 6)	60.00	65.00	67.50	65.00	62.50	64.00 (21.20)

Scores represent group mean comprehension percentages. Period 2 n=17, period 4 n=17, period 6 n=16.

Figure 1

Mean comprehension scores by background music condition. SD=Standard deviation. Left panel shows the overall mean with standard deviation error bars. The Right panel shows trial-by-trial trends across the five sessions. Period 2 n=17, period 4 n=17, period 6 n=16. Data collected by the author (2025).

Comprehension scores were recorded for each group in the five days of trials, with an average score for each day. The instrumental Spanish music background condition produced the highest overall mean score across all five trials, at 75.06% and a standard deviation of 22.45, close to the silence background condition, 72.71% and a standard deviation of 20.67, and the instrumental English music condition, 64.47% with a standard deviation of 21.20. Across the five days of trials, the instrumental English music condition scored the lowest in every trial. Several patterns are worth noting across these trials. The gap between the English music condition and the other two conditions was notably consistent across the trials, with an approximate range of 10 to 15 percentage points below the silence group and the instrumental Spanish group. The Spanish music and silence conditions had similar averages in comparison scores across most trials. Instrumental Spanish music outperformed trials 4 and 5, giving them the overall highest average comprehension score. The silence condition did well on the first trial day and had a slow decline in their average comprehension score, staying strong in trials one through three, which may suggest that the group had a stabilizing effect on sustained attention in the repeated sessions, though this interpretation should be treated cautiously given the sample size (Hallam et al., 2002). The narrowed gap between Spanish music and silence, 2.4 percentage

points overall, underscores the primary finding, which is the consistent underperformance of the English music condition rather than a large advantage of Spanish music over silence.

Beyond the means of comprehension scores, the standard deviation across the three conditions is notably large, with a range of 15 to 25 within each individual trial. The figures indicate considerable variability in individual performance within each condition across every trial. Consistent with prior research identifying individual differences. Particularly, personal study habits and personality traits are meaningful moderating variables in the background music experiment (Goltz & Sadakata, 2021). It may be possible that some students within each condition were helped, unaffected, or hindered by their randomly assigned music background condition in ways that the group means alone do not capture. The median scores further reinforce the pattern that was shown in the mean scores. Across all five trials combined, the silence and Spanish music conditions both produced a median score of 80, while the English music condition produced a median of 60. This means the middle-performing students in the English music group consistently score a full 20 points lower than the middle-performing students in either of the other two conditions, suggesting that the lower mean of the English music group was not simply driven by a small number of outliers but reflected a broader suppression of performance across participants in that condition.

Discussion

Limitations

There are several limitations of this study that should be acknowledged when interpreting the findings. First, the sample size within each condition was modest, with groups running from seventeen to eighteen students. This limits the generalizability and statistical power of any comparison between group means and reduces the experiments results to be applied beyond the participating school and student population, not giving a full representation of students in central florida. Secondly, participants were not pre-screened for personal music listening habits before the experiment. Research often identified individual study habits as a meaningful moderating variable, with students who habitually study with music responding differently to background music conditions than those who prefer silence (Goltz & Sadakata, 2021). The absence of this information makes it difficult to determine whether observed differences reflect the music condition itself or already made individual tendencies, and prior association with performing better under certain conditions. Thirdly, the limitations of the experiment are furthered by the internal validity of individual participants' effort and engagement. Because the comprehension task was administered as a brief in-class activity rather than a formal graded assessment, it is possible that some students did not put forth full effort on every trial, introducing noise into the data that is unrelated to the music condition, but rather an outcome of the students' effort level. This is reflected in the large standard deviations observed across the three trial groups, where scores of 20 appeared in every condition across multiple trials; which may suggest that at least some participants may have disengaged on certain days. This could have happened for many reasons. Future research could address this by framing the task as a graded assignment or by incorporating a brief engagement check to flag responses that appear to reflect minimal effort (Goltz & Sadakata, 2021). Additionally, the participants' pool was not screened for native or heritage Spanish speakers. Students who speak Spanish at home would

likely have a meaningfully different baseline compared to students who are L2 learners having little Spanish exposure and only being able to practice their Spanish in the classroom, and their scores could have disproportionately inflated the mean of whichever condition they were assigned to. This represents a confounding variable that was controlled for in the current design. Future research should replicate the experiment, screen participants for home language background, and either exclude heritage speakers or treat them as a separate subgroup in the analysis: as their relationship to the language and to Spanish music specifically may differ substantially from classroom-only learners (Erten & Razi, 2009). The time of day at which each class period meets also represents a potential confounding variable. Period two met earlier in the school day than period four and period six, meaning that there may have been fatigue and cognitive depletion accumulated across the day that may have differentially affected the English music group, who met later in the day, being the last group to have the experiment run on; independently of the music condition itself. Research on cognitive performance and time of day suggests that students tend to perform better on academic tasks earlier in the school day when mental fatigue is lower, and that performance on reading and comprehension tasks can decline as the day progresses (Sun et al., 2024). Ideally, the three groups participating in the experiment would have completed each trial at the same hour in the same class period to reduce and account for any fatigue that might have built up throughout the day; having the trials done in the same class period could account for this. Since this was not possible within a natural classroom setting, the time-of-day differences between the groups should be acknowledged as a potential alternative explanation for the consistently lower scores of the English music group. Lastly, and most significantly, no inferential statistical testing was applied to the data without a one-way ANOVA or similar analysis; it is not possible to determine whether the differences observed

between the group means are statistically significant or simply a product of natural score variation across the small sample size. The findings should therefore be treated as descriptive and exploratory rather than confirmatory. Future research addressing these limitations, through larger samples, participant pre-screening, and formal statistical analysis, would substantially strengthen the conclusion about whether linguistically aligned instrumental music reliably benefits L2 reading comprehension.

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